

GENDER AND REGIONAL DIFFERENCES IN THE PREVALENCE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION AND ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE

Akhmedov A.T. ¹Sharipov Zh.R. ²¹ PhD., Associate Professor, Pediatric Surgery and Neurosurgery,
Bukhara State Medical Institute, Bukhara, 200100, Uzbekistan² Head of department, ICU, Bukhara Branch of Republican
Specialized Cardiology Scientific-Practical Medicine center, Bukhara,
200100, Uzbekistan

E-mail: axmedov.ahad@bsmi.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17292026>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st October 2025

Accepted: 04th October 2025

Online: 08th October 2025

KEYWORDS

In this regard, there is a need for studies that will reveal the influence of gender, regional and anthropometric characteristics on the development and course of hypertension and coronary heart disease.

ABSTRACT

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) remain the leading causes of global mortality, annually claiming the lives of more than 18 million people [1,2]. Arterial hypertension (AH) and coronary heart disease (CHD) are the main factors determining the development of critical vascular complications. According to global statistics [3], AH affects over 1.2 billion people, and CHD has been diagnosed in more than 126 million. The combination of these pathologies is especially common in people over 60 years of age, reaching 45–50%, which is associated with the progressive impact of such factors as excess body weight, lipid metabolism disorders, and chronic inflammation [3,4,9].

Introduction: Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) remain the leading causes of global mortality, annually claiming the lives of more than 18 million people [1,2]. Arterial hypertension (AH) and coronary heart disease (CHD) are the main factors determining the development of critical vascular complications. According to global statistics [3], AH affects over 1.2 billion people, and CHD has been diagnosed in more than 126 million. The combination of these pathologies is especially common in people over 60 years of age, reaching 45–50%, which is associated with the progressive impact of such factors as excess body weight, lipid metabolism disorders, and chronic inflammation [3,4,9].

Current approaches to the treatment and prevention of CVD do not fully solve the problem of effective hypertension management: in 35–40% of patients, blood pressure remains above target values, which significantly increases the risk of developing coronary heart disease and other cardiovascular events. Uncontrolled hypertension is associated with an increase in mortality from CVD, reaching 15–20% per decade [5,8]. The transition from isolated hypertension to a combination with coronary heart disease is due to complex processes, including vascular remodeling, microcirculatory disorders, and systemic metabolic shifts, but the detailed mechanisms of this process remain poorly understood [6,7].

In this regard, there is a need for studies that will reveal the influence of gender, regional and anthropometric characteristics on the development and course of hypertension and coronary heart disease. Such data can become the basis for improving the methods of early prediction and prevention, which emphasizes the importance of this study.

Purpose of the study. to study gender and regional characteristics of arterial hypertension and coronary heart disease.

Materials and methods. To conduct the study, a comprehensive clinical and laboratory examination of 120 patients who were undergoing inpatient and outpatient treatment at the Bukhara Regional Cardiology Dispensary was conducted. All study participants were carefully selected taking into account the inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure maximum reliability of the data obtained and exclude the influence of concomitant pathologies. Patients were divided into two main clinical groups depending on the established diagnosis:

Group I included 60 patients suffering from hypertension. These patients were diagnosed with primary hypertension, without obvious signs of coronary heart disease, which allowed us to focus on the characteristics of the hypertensive process.

Group II consisted of 60 patients with an established diagnosis of coronary heart disease that developed against the background of hypertension. These patients represented a more complex clinical category, since the combination of two diseases significantly worsens the course and prognosis of cardiovascular disorders.

The control group consisted of 20 conditionally healthy individuals with no history of chronic cardiovascular diseases, which was confirmed by clinical examination and additional instrumental diagnostic methods.

Conclusions:

1. In patients with isolated hypertension, a significant predominance of women was noted - 61.7%, while among patients with a combination of hypertension and coronary heart disease, the proportion of men was 51.7%. Women were more common in group I (37 out of 60), while men predominated in group II (31 out of 60), but these differences did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.144$).

2. Rural residents predominated among patients with isolated hypertension - 80.0%, while in patients with hypertension and coronary heart disease their proportion was 71.7%. The urban population was more common in group II - 28.3% compared to 20.0% in group I, although the differences did not reach significance ($p = 0.292$).

3. Excess body weight was more often recorded in patients with isolated hypertension - 50.0%, while among patients with a combination of hypertension and coronary heart disease this figure was 40.0%. The proportion of individuals with normal BMI in group II was higher - 30.0% versus 10.0% in group I, which reflects statistically significant differences in the distribution of BMI ($p=0.049$).

References:

1. Akhmedov, A. T., & Sharipov, Z. R. (2023). The role of cytokines in the development of arterial hypertension. *Int J Med Sci Clin Res*, 3(03), 59-67.
2. A.T. Akhmedov (2024). IMPACT OF CYTOKINES ON THE ONSET AND PROGRESSION OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 4 (6), 116-123. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12154505.
3. Chazova I.E., Zhernakova Yu.V. Modern approaches to the treatment of arterial hypertension in patients with coronary heart disease // *Therapeutic archive*. - 2021. - Vol. 93. - No. 6. - P. 678-685.
4. Khakimov Z.K., Saidova M.A. Regional features of the prevalence of risk factors for cardiovascular diseases in Uzbekistan // *New Day in Medicine*. - 2022. - No. 3. - P. 150-154.
5. Barbarash O.L. et al. The impact of obesity on the prognosis in patients with coronary heart disease: data from a cohort study // *Cardiology*. - 2023. - Vol. 63. - No. 2. - P. 34-41.
6. Zagidullin N.Sh., Zagidullina L.R. Epidemiology of ischemic heart disease depending on place of residence: city vs village // *Practical medicine*. - 2020. - No. 5. - P. 19-25.
7. Ridker PM et al. Inflammation, obesity, and risk of ischemic heart disease: a prospective cohort study // *The Lancet*. - 2015. - V. 385. - P. 1234-1241.

-
8. Stamler J. et al. Obesity and cardiovascular risk: insights from the Framingham Heart Study // American Journal of Cardiology. – 2019. – V. 123. – P. 145-152.
9. Rosendorff C. et al. Treatment of hypertension in patients with coronary artery disease: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association // Journal of the American College of Cardiology. – 2015. – V. 65. – P. 1998-2038.

